

Twelve Month Report 2020

**JRP13-AMRSH5-
WORLD COM**

Responsible Partner: P25-NUIG

Contributing partners:

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>

<i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Other international stakeholder(s):		
	Social Media:		
	Other recipient(s):		

TITLE

1. Summary of the work carried out

500 words, 1 page. Please emphasize the main scientific results and outcomes. Pay special attention to the impact the project may have for the OHEJP and its stakeholders. This part will be published and should therefore be clear on its own. The CommsTeam may use this summary for communication means.

The OneHealth WorldCOM project aims to develop on-site diagnostic tools, linked with mobile referencing technology, for detection of AMR zoonotic pathogens (*Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*) in agricultural and environmental settings. The impact for OHEJP and stakeholders will be rapid on-site detection of AMR pathogens in animal and human populations. Technologies under development will facilitate investigation of potential emerging resistances at earlier stages than currently feasible. Data generated will be used to develop machine-learning algorithms to predict AMR in various environments.

Recruitment of staff has been completed by most partners, and considerable progress made on a number of tasks. All *bla* antimicrobial resistance genes present in *Salmonella*, *E.coli*, *Klebsiella* and *Acinetobacter* genomes were extracted from the NCBI Pathogens database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogens/isolates#/search/>). All types and subtypes of Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBLs) and plasmid-mediated colistin resistance genes have been analysed for frequency among reported and extracted sequences (UoS). High frequency resistance gene subtypes have been highlighted for further sequence analysis to illustrate geographic distribution and geography-specific single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). The prevalence of ESBL subtypes in bacterial pathogens and a sequence database of the selected alleles have been published in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4019839).

Targeted and whole-genome sequencing of AMR strains has been undertaken. This includes: *de novo* sequencing and genome assembly of AMR *E.coli* strains; 88 *Campylobacter* spp. strains have been genome sequenced, genomes assembled, and MLST types assigned (UT); aminoglycoside and beta-lactam resistant Enterobacteria from companion animals, leading to identification of new epidemic plasmids that will be studied within the Consortium in different countries; 50 plazomicin-resistant Enterobacteria isolated from a single location from animals, sewage, wastewater, humans and food (UCM); *E.coli* strains resistant to 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins isolated from swine and alpaca hosts; a subset of 30 strains, characterised with respect to phylogeny, antimicrobial-resistance patterns and plasmid profile and whole-genome-sequenced (FLI); *E.coli* CTX-M environmental samples (NUIG); and *E.coli* isolates resistant to 3rd and 4th-generation cephalosporins and/or carbapenemes and/or colistin from human and animal origin (INSA).

LAMP assay development has been substantially progressed including the development and validation of a duplex CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of *E.coli* CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15 isolates (NUIG). The duplex assay has been transferred to another WorldCOM partner (FLI) for further testing and validation using veterinary samples. LAMP assays targeted at plasmid-mediated colistin resistance (*mcr-1* gene), KPC-mediated carbapenem resistance, oxacillin-hydrolyzing β -lactamases (OXA-48 gene) and the most frequent alleles of the OXA-48-like variants, have also been developed and validated (UoS), demonstrating detection of AMR target genes within 3-5 minutes. Good progress has also been made on the development and evaluation of rapid DNA extraction protocols for use in the field. This includes the detection of AMR genes from water samples, demonstrating the detection of the *mcr-1* target gene with a detection limit of 10² cfu/mL as confirmed by culture. LAMP assays targeting AMR genes coupled with optimised sample-preparation methods will be crucial for on-site detection of AMR in different settings.

2. Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

5000 words, 10 pages. Please provide enough detail to understand the work done per task, without additional information. All aspects should be discussed, scientific and others (integrative activities, etc.).

WP: 1 Generation of up to date sequence information for selected pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes (M25-M36)

Task 1 (WP1-T1): Analysis of publically available sequences for antimicrobial resistance genes associated with Salmonella, Campylobacter and E. coli (M25-M28)

At the UoS, all *bla* antimicrobial resistance genes present in *Salmonella*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* and *Acinetobacter* genomes have been extracted from NCBI Pathogens database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogens/isolates#/search/>). For the initial phase of this work package, we have focused on ESBL-related AMR genes. As these genes are absent from *Campylobacter*, we have not included this bacterium in these analyses, and have instead, used the important pathogens *Klebsiella* and *Acinetobacter*. Later work will include antibiotic resistances relevant to *Campylobacter*. All types and subtypes of Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBLs) and plasmid-mediated colistin resistance genes have been analysed for frequency among reported and extracted sequences. High frequency resistance gene subtypes have been highlighted for further sequence analysis to illustrate geographic distribution and geographic-specific single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). The Prevalence of ESBL subtypes in bacterial pathogens and a sequence database of the selected alleles have been published in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4019839). This task has been completed.

Task 2 (WP1-T2): Targeted and whole genome de novo sequencing of phenotypically characterised isolates from various settings (M25-M42)

In the UK, no whole genome sequencing has been performed due to the COVID-19 lock down and it is currently postponed. However, the task is still ongoing.

In Estonia 120 *E. coli* strains have been *de novo* sequenced and genomes assembled. The bioinformatic analysis of these genomes, i.e. annotation and prediction of the genes, is ongoing. In addition, 88 *Campylobacter* spp. strains have been *de novo* sequenced, genomes assembled and MLST types assigned. A manuscript is planned for submission in Jan-Feb 2021 based on preliminary analysis of these *Campylobacter* sp. strains.

At UCM, plazomizin-resistant isolates are being analysed. Interestingly, studying plazomizin resistance, an emerging resistant gene has been identified, *npmA*. This gene is present in a novel Transposon within a new Integrative Conjugative Element (ICE). Further, emergence of plazomizin resistance in pig-farms is being identified in enterobacteria highly resistant to aminoglycosides and beta-lactams that have been sequenced using Illumina and Nanopore sequencing, leading to the identification of new epidemic plasmids that will be studied within the Consortium in different countries. Further, a new IncR epidemic plasmid has been identified in a horse *Enterobacter hormaechei* ST171 -clone. This is an epidemic clone, responsible for several epidemics in pediatric Hospitals in the USA. Tracjking of this plasmid-world-in the Consortium is envisaged.

At FLI, *E. coli* strains resistant to 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins were isolated from swine and alpaca hosts. A subset of 30 strains was selected, characterized with respect to phylogeny,
[Date] [name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

antimicrobial resistance pattern and plasmid profile and is currently being whole-genome-sequenced (Illumina) and analysed.

NUI Galway provided genomic nucleotide sequence information from locally isolated *E. coli* CTX-M environmental samples to a WorldCOM AMR gene sequence database for use in assay development. This nucleotide sequence information included 2 x CTX-M-1, 1 x CTX-M-9, 4 x CTX-M-4, 24 x CTX-M-15, 5 x CTX-M-27 and 1 x CTX-M-65 *E. coli* isolates.

At INSA, *E. coli* isolates resistant to 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins and/or resistant to carbapenemes and/or resistant to colistin from human and animal origin were sequenced using a MiSeq Illumina platform. Bioinformatic analysis was performed using command line pipelines and the respective results are being shared with the other partners.

Task 3 (WP1-T3): Development of machine learning algorithms for the prediction of anti-microbial resistance. (University of Surrey, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM) (M37-M42)

The start date for this task has been partially delayed as Dr Gardner only recently joined the UoS School of Veterinary Medicine. At UCM using the inhouse tool ARUflow together with targeted search in world-wide sequencing projects, we have identified and epidemic in a Ducth Hospital of a new emerging plazomicin-resistant bacterium.

Work-package 2 Assay Development (M36-M45)

Task 1 (WP2-T1): Development and performance evaluation of singleplex isothermal amplification assays for selected AMR gene targets (M31-M39)

NUI Galway completed the design of singleplex isothermal nucleic acid amplification assays for the detection of the selected AMR associated CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15 gene targets. This initial assay design was achieved using existing genomic sequence data of *E.coli* isolates from environmental samples collected and processed by NUI Galway. These *E. coli* isolates contained CTX-M Group 1 variants, type 1 and 15. Sequence alignment analysis was used to identify single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) differences between the type 1 and 15 variants. These SNP differences were subsequently used to develop loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assays to detect and differentiate the type 1 and 15 variants. Standard LAMP assays were also designed to detect both CTX-M Group 1 variants. Evaluation of these assays successfully identified an optimal CTX-M-1 LEC-LAMP assay that detects CTX-M-1 targets while differentiating CTX-M-15 targets. The oligonucleotide probe used in the CTX-M-1 LEC-LAMP was modified to contain a different fluorophore label to enable detection of the CTX-M-15 target, while differentiating CTX-M-1. For development of an internal amplification (IAC) control assay, a synthetic DNA template and corresponding LEC-LAMP assay was developed. All three singleplex LEC-LAMP assays for the detection of CTX-M-1, CTX-M-15 and the IAC template were then optimised and evaluated. The analytical sensitivity of each assay demonstrated low limits-of-detection with 10 genome copies detected in under 30 min. Each assay demonstrated 100% analytical specificity with 10 *E. coli* CTX-M-1 isolates and 25 *E. coli* CTX-M-15 isolates correctly identified by each corresponding LEC-LAMP assay. These assays would subsequently be used in WP2 Task 3 to develop multiplex LEC-LAMP assays.

At the UoS, *mcr*, *bla_{OXA}*, *bla_{CTX-M}*, *bla_{NDM}* and *bla_{KPC}* gene sequences have been extracted from genomes listed in the NCBI Pathogens database to represent all gene alleles. This showed the conserved regions across the different alleles of each *mcr*, *bla_{KPC}* and *bla_{OXA-48}* subtypes and the homology across the selected subtypes. The extracted sequences showed a species-specific trend across *mcr* gene subtypes

with *mcr-1* being the most predominant in *E. coli*, *mcr-8* in *Klebsiella* and *mcr-9* in *Salmonella*. MSA of *bla*_{KPC} genes showed 99% homology among *bla*_{KPC-2} gene sequence alleles, while MSA of all *bla*_{KPC} genes and corresponding alleles showed 93% conserved homology. Thus, conserved regions were used to design LAMP primer sets for *mcr-1*, *mcr-8*, *mcr-9*, all *bla*_{KPC}, *bla*_{OXA-48} and some of the *bla*_{OXA-48-like} genes (OXA-48, OXA-232, OXA-181 and OXA-54 encoding genes) using both LAMP Designer 1.15 and Primer Explorer V5.

After optimisation, the KPC LAMP assay was able to detect all KPC positive strains including two *K. pneumoniae* clinical strains, *E. coli* and *E. cloacae* within 4 min, while all control strains, including a diverse range of Gram-negative and -positive bacteria, remained negative. The KPC LAMP assay demonstrated good sensitivity and a detection limit of approximately 10 pg DNA (successfully amplified within 9 mins). The *mcr-1* LAMP assay was also able to detect all *mcr-1* positive isolates including *E. coli* and *S. Typhimurium* within 4 min with good specificity with regards to all control strains. The *mcr-1* assay demonstrated a detection limit of approximately 1 pg DNA, which was successfully amplified at 11 min. The OXA-48 LAMP assay was tested against a wide range of *bla*_{OXA-48} and *bla*_{OXA-48-like} *K. pneumoniae* and *E. coli* isolates and successfully detected the target gene within 3-5 min. The test panel included some of the *bla*_{OXA-48} alleles, including OXA-181, OXA-232 and OXA-244 and they were successfully detected. The panel also included OXA-48 negative controls of *K. pneumoniae* and *E. coli* isolates, and *A. baumannii* OXA-23, OXA-25 and *P. aeruginosa* OXA-50. All negative controls were negative except for OXA-25 and OXA-50 isolates, which were amplified at a very low rate, suggesting the amplification was not specific. Further optimisation is ongoing to improve the assay specificity, assess the detection limit and design specific LAMP assays for *bla*_{OXA-23}, *bla*_{OXA-25} and *bla*_{OXA-50} if possible.

The task is still ongoing.

Task 2 (WP2-T2) : Evaluation and selection of sample preparation methods for use with laboratory and on-site tests (M31-M39)

NUI Galway has developed and evaluated a modified Chelex® 100 heat lysis extraction method for rapid on-site DNA extraction from bovine and porcine faecal samples. Optimisation and evaluation of this extraction method was carried out using *E. coli* CTX-M-1 and *E. coli* CTX-M-15 isolates spiked into bovine and porcine faecal samples. This extraction protocol can be carried out using portable equipment in approximately 15-20 min and the current resulting LEC-LAMP limit-of-detection is approximately 50 CFU/uL for *E. coli* CTX-M-1 and *E. coli* CTX-M-15 spiked into bovine or porcine faecal samples. Further evaluation of the modified Chelex® 100 heat lysis extraction method will be carried out using alpaca and porcine faecal samples previously confirmed to be positive for *E. coli* CTX-M-1 and *E. coli* CTX-M-15, supplied by FLI.

UoS has initiated work on the development and evaluation of water sample preparation methods for the detection of targeted AMR LAMP assays. Initial LAMP testing was performed using *mcr-1* LAMP and spiking of an *mcr-1* positive *E. coli* strain in tap water for validation of the sample preparation methods. After optimisations, a water sample preparation method has been finalised. The method involves centrifugation of the water samples to precipitate the bacterial content followed by resuspension in extraction buffer and heat shock treatment for bacterial lysis. The method is advantageous in being rapid, only taking 30 min. Spiked water samples were successfully amplified within 30 min of sample preparation and the *mcr-1* LAMP assay successfully detected up to 10² cfu/mL (as confirmed by culture) at 11 min of amplification. Further validation is ongoing to confirm detection limit and assess the sample preparation method using different water sources and AMR targets. The task is still ongoing.

Task 3 (WP2-T3) : Development and performance evaluation of multiplex assays for pathogens and resistance genes (M36-M45)

At NUIG the singleplex CTX-M-1, CTX-M-15 and IAC LEC-LAMP assays were combined to develop various duplex LEC-LAMP assays. The IAC LEC-LAMP assay was separately combined with the CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15 LEC-LAMP assays, creating internally controlled two-target assays. No cross reactivity was observed between the IAC LEC-LAMP assay and the CTX-M-1 or CTX-M-15 LEC-LAMP assays, and no significant differences observed in limit-of-detection or time-to-positivity values between the singleplex and duplex assays. Combination of the CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15 LEC-LAMP assays to develop a duplex CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay required minor primer re-design. The duplex CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay demonstrated similar limit-of-detection and time-to-positivity values to the corresponding singleplex assays, and also successful differentiation between all 10 *E. coli* CTX-M-1 isolates and all 25 *E. coli* CTX-M-15 isolates. Minor IAC LEC-LAMP probe redesign involving alteration of the fluorophore labelling is required for incorporation of the IAC LEC-LAMP assay with the duplex CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP, to develop a triplex internally controlled CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay. Future work will involve evaluation of this multiplex LEC-LAMP assay on-site.

Work-package 5 Project Management (M25-M54)

Task 1 (WP5-T1) - Project Management (M25-M54)

A WorldCOM consortium KOM was held on January 26th and 27th 2020 in Brussels, at which WP and Task priorities were agreed. Subsequent WorldCOM consortium meetings have taken place via Zoom meetings held monthly from March 2020 (March 24th; April 28th; May 20th; June 2nd; October 2nd). The consortium had planned a further consortium meeting to review progress and for future project planning in Prague, during the OHEJP ASM in May. However, the planned meeting was replaced with a Zoom meeting on June 2nd.

A WorldCOM DMP based on the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP was developed according to guidance provided by the OHEJP WP4 team in their D4.7 Guidelines for Data Management Plan implementation. The DMP was submitted (deliverable D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.2) and is available on the DMP group of the OHEJP website. WorldCOM DMP leader Liam Burke attended online training on August 5th 2020 for the new OHEJP online data management platform CDP. A data management guide and DMP Excel template for WorldCOM has been prepared for task leaders to help them comply with the DMP. Liam Burke will update the CDP application with details of WorldCOM data throughout the project, with information provided to him by task leaders on their datasets using the Excel template. The OHEJP WP4 team reviewed and approved WorldCOM's online DMP in December 2020.

3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

The following list refers to the deliverables and milestones as mentioned in the AWP Y3 (2020). WP3/WP4 Team pre-filled this table with available information. Please verify, correct if needed, complete and make sure that all deliverables are uploaded on the private project group of the website and on Zenodo. Note that all deliverables should be public. . In case where some deliverables or manuscripts could not be made public, this should be explained and an estimation of the date where these documents will become public should be provided here.

Please note that you should indicate any delay due to COVID-19.

Deliverables

WP3/WP4 Team pre-filled the table below with available information. Please verify, correct if needed and complete.

JRP /JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments <i>(Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
13	D-JPR13-AMR2.1-WP1.1	Generation of a sequence database comprising publically available and newly generated sequences for <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> and <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. and resistance genes CTX-M-15, NDM-5, KPC-2, OXA-48 and MCR-1.	M30 – June 30 th 2020		M33 – 30th September 2020		Zenodo link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4019840 . Confidential on relevant WorldCOM OHEJP website section, and already shared with all consortium members during development.	3

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JRP /JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments <i>(Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP1.2	Novel machine learning algorithms for the prediction and detection of AMR from genomic sequences.	M 36 – December 2020		M 42 – June 2021	Delayed recruitment & and laboratory work	Deliverables will be made public, but elements of the data included in the deliverable may be embargoed or kept confidential, in line with the OHEJP guidelines.	4
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.1	Kick-off meeting organised	M 26 – February 2020	M 25 – January 27 th 2020	N/A	N/A	Confidential	Other – Project Management
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.2	Project Specific Data Management Plan prepared	M30 – June 30 th 2020	M33 – September 9th 2020	N/A	No – due to CMP platform delay	Confidential on relevant WorldCOM OHEJP website section, and already shared with all consortium members during development.	3
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.3	Project review meeting organised	33	M33 – September 9th 2020	September 2020		Virtual Meeting held due to COVID-19 restrictions	Other – Project Management
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-	Technical and financial reports prepared for	M 36 – December		M 38	No	Confidential to WorldCOM and OHEJP	Other – Project

[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

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JRP /JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments <i>(Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
	WP5.4	submission	2020					Management

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

Milestones

Please verify and correct, if needed

WP3/WP4 Team pre-filled the table below with available information. Please verify, correct if needed and complete.

JRP/JIPCCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-01	Generation of sequence information for pathogens and resistance genes of interest.	M30 – June 30th 2020	No	M42 – June 2021	Delayed due to COVID-19 and country-wide lockdowns.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-02	Transfer of relevant sequence information for development and training of novel machine learning algorithms.	36 – December 2020	No	M 42 – June 2021	Delayed due to COVID-19 and late recruitment
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-03	Singleplex assays for the detection of pathogens including <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> and <i>E. coli</i> and CTX-M-15, KPC-2, NDM-5, OXA-48 and MCR-1 genes	36	No	M 39 – March 2021	Singleplex assays for CTX-M-1/15, KPC, NDM-5, OXA-48, OXA-48-like and MCR-1/8/9 genes representing major AMR determinants. Delayed due to COVID-19 and country-wide lockdowns.

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JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-04	Sample preparation methods evaluated	36	No	M 39 – March 2021	Delayed due to COVID-19 and country-wide lock-downs.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-05	Organisation of kick-off meeting	M 26 February 2020	M25 – January 27 th 2020	N/A	N/A
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-06	Preparation of technical and financial reports for submission	36	No	M 38 – February 2021	

[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

4. Publications and additional outputs

Please, make sure that OHEJP funding is acknowledged in publications and other outputs

List peer-reviewed publications (please mention whether these are registered in **OpenAIRE**) and others. For every publication please specify:

- **Doi reference**
- **Repository link**
- **Gold or green open access?**
 - o *If golden: Please specify the costs of the publication*
 - o *If green: Length of the Embargo, if any. Open access to the publication must be ensured within a maximum of six months.*

If no doi reference (e.g. article in journal, publication in conference proceedings or workshop, book or monograph, chapter in a book, thesis/Dissertation, other), please provide as much information as possible.

We have noticed that sometimes the Consortium members publish manuscripts where the One Health EJP is acknowledged, but the information is not included in the reports. Could you please contact the Consortium members and ask them to report all the One Health EJP publications?

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)

Additional output

Any non-peer review papers and other outcomes can be mentioned here: grey publication, folder or leaflet, poster, video, tools, guidelines, patents etc. These should not be included if they are deliverables. Please provide information about where the outputs can be accessed and, additionally, if it is the final version of the output or whether the work is ongoing.

None to date

5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

Shortly describe what links and collaborations exist with other projects, within or outside One Health EJP, and with networks like ECDC and EFSA. Indicate complementarities.

.NUI Galway participates in the MedVetKlebs OHEJP project, and is a member of the Med-Vet-Net association. Prof Morris is part of a JPIAMR network aimed at identifying robust, measurable surveillance indicators and methodologies for the monitoring of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the environment.

FLI participates in the JPIAMR consortia HECTOR and OASIS. HECTOR aims to identify determinants of host restriction of *Escherichia coli* strains and their potential association with AMR transmission and prevalence. OASIS aims to develop an AMR surveillance strategy, based on the Lot Quality Assurance Sampling approach, in a One Health context, and applicable in high-, middle-, and low-income countries.

UCM participates in the AVANT EU project, in ARDIG and FARMED, both from OH EJP, as well as in the MSCA CARTNET. Currently, UCM is preparing a Project for the JPI-AMR call on One health interventions (13th call). Input from these projects will be relevant for WORLDCOM, and active participation between OHEJP projects will be encouraged for the benefit of OHEJP. Further, several TCs were organized between Dr. Burke and Prof. Gonzalez-Zorn to organize a visit to Madrid for training and organizing common research projects. The application for Short Term Missions in OH EJP has been approved, and Dr. Burke will visit the lab at UCM in Summer 2021. We hope that the epidemic situation will allow for this visit.

UT participates in the FED-AMR from OH EJP and Intereg Baltic Sea Region seed money project VETMED (Veterinary medication and its impact on antimicrobial resistance in the environment).

INSA also participates in other OHEJP projects, such as FED-AMR and FULL-FORCE.

We are fully convinced that at the end of the project the tool obtained will be very useful, so it will be presented to EFSA, ECDC, and EURL AMR.

6. Data Management Plan

The DMP of the project should be available. Please indicate where it can be found.

Does the DMP comprise descriptions of all the data generated in the project?

Are the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles fulfilled? If not, please explain.

1. *Have you uploaded a first version of the project's DMP to the DMP group on the OHEJP website?*

A first PDF version has been uploaded to the WorldCOM page5 on the OHEJP website. The "live" DMP is available on the Lisam Collaborative Data Platform (CDP) DMP online tool <https://apps.lisam.com/app/#Apps/CDP>. This comprises descriptions of all the data generated in the project and functions as an index of where the data is stored which complies with the FAIR principles.

The DMP coordinator (Dr Liam Burke) completed CDP training in August 2020 and then updated the CDP platform with information on WorldCOM data from task leaders. Feedback on the WorldCOM DMP was received in December from the WP4 team and was overall positive, with some instructions for improvements, which have been implemented. Dr Burke will continuously update the CDP tool with information provided to him by task leaders on their datasets using the DMP Excel template.

2. *Have you encountered any problems or difficulties when setting up and updating the DMP? If yes, please specify.*

Yes, the DMP coordinator (Dr Liam Burke) was unable to create a DMP using the originally indicated online tool at <https://dmponline.be/>. However, he was able to access the DMPs of other consortia through the DMP group on the OHEJP website. He used these DMPs, plus the D4.7 Guidelines for Data Management Plan implementation for guidance in developing the WorldCOM DMP. The CDP platform has since become available and this has been updated with information on WorldCOM data provided by task leaders.

7. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Projects 2nd round

WP3/WP4 Team pre-filled the table below with available information. Please clearly explain the actions and measures that have been taken to comply with the recommendations you received from the Ethics Advisors

Requirements of ethical reviewers in 2020	What measures and actions do you propose?	Comments of Ethics Advisors, November 2020	Comments Project Leaders, January 2021	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2021	Comments Project Leaders, January 2022
Copy of the ethical approval from the NUI's REC must be presented.	NUI Galway has no plans currently to analyse human biological samples as part of the WorldCOM project, hence no Ethics REC approval has been requested to date.	Satisfactory reply. Please update your ethical submission if this should change in any way			
The beneficiaries must provide the contact address of the Data Protector Officer of the institution in charge of processing the data obtained	Data Protector Officer contacts are available from the WorldCOM partners upon request	Satisfactory reply			
As 'spread of AMR will be investigated in people living in proximity to farms' (p14/26), the beneficiaries must confirm that, if relevant, appropriate	No human samples will be collected in the context of this study. We will only re-analyse DNA extracted from bacterial strains in our stocks.	Satisfactory reply. Please update your ethical submission if this should change in any way			

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
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authorizations will be sought to collect human samples.					
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[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

8. List of critical risks

Please indicate possible risk within your JRP/JIP

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	
Delay in work plan execution	
Conflicts within the consortium	
Lack of commitment of partners	
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	
Poor intra-project relationship	
Potential entry/exit of partners	
Other risks (please describe)	Additional sampling of animals may become difficult, due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic.

Additional information

9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Please fill in one table per event you attended/organised in 2020. You should also register these activities online on the OneHealth EJP webpage : <https://onehealthjep.eu/internal-events-survey/>

Name of the activity:	Conference participation		
Date:	27 – 29 May 2020		
Place:	OHEJP Virtual ASM meeting		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Centre for One Health Spotlight Series: COVID-19 – A One Health Challenge		
Date:	July 27 th 2020		
Place:	Online – via Zoom and YouTube		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	57	Media	
Industry	22	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	10	Other	
Policy Makers	8		

Name of the activity:	Academy of Medical Students of Ireland		
Date:	November 5 th 2020		
Place:	Online – via Zoom		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Newspaper Article – Irish Examiner		
Date:	November 18 th 2020		
Place:			
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release	Yes	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	24,574	Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Pfizer AMR Event		
Date:	November 19 th 2020		
Place:	Online via Zoom		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	20	Media	
Industry	80	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Centre for One Health Spotlight Series – AMR: A One Health Challenge		
Date:	November 20 th 2020		
Place:	Online – via Zoom and YouTube		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	56	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	5	Other	
Policy Makers	3		

Name of the activity:	EPA/HSE/ESRI Environment, Health and Wellbeing Virtual conference		
Date:	November 26 th 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	85	Media	3
Industry	86	Investors	
Civil Society	15	Customers	
General Public	10	Other	
Policy Makers	73		

Name of the activity:	Social Media Promotional Activities		
Date:	Numerous dates throughout 2020		
Place:	Twitter		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes (tweets about WorldCOM & OHEJP)	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Newspaper Article – Irish Times		
Date:	January 11 th 2021		
Place:			
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release	Yes	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	79,021	Other	
Policy Makers			